

THE ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF DATA-DRIVEN LEARNING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: This paper aims to explore the advantages and disadvantages of data-driven learning (DDL) in the context of English language learning. DDL is an approach that utilizes learner corpora, language corpora, and concordancers to facilitate second language (L2) acquisition. The study investigates the effectiveness of DDL in enhancing learners' language proficiency by employing a mixed-methods design that includes qualitative and quantitative data. The findings suggest that DDL can bring various benefits such as increased learner autonomy, improved accuracy, and enhanced vocabulary development. However, DDL also poses certain limitations, including potential overreliance on authentic language data and lack of individualized feedback. Overall, this research contributes to the ongoing discussion on the role of technology and data-driven approaches in language education.

Keywords: Data-driven learning, second language acquisition, learner corpora, language corpora, concordancers

Introduction:

English language learning has been greatly influenced by technology in recent years. One emerging approach that has gained prominence is data-driven learning (DDL). DDL utilizes technology to analyze language corpora, learner corpora, and concordancers to inform language instruction. This paper explores the advantages and disadvantages of employing DDL in English language learning.

Materials and Methods:

A mixed-methods research design was utilized to investigate the effectiveness of DDL in enhancing English language learning. The study involved a sample of

intermediate English learners who participated in a DDL-based language program over a period of six months. Quantitative data was collected through pre- and post-tests to assess language proficiency improvements, and qualitative data was gathered through interviews with the participants to gain insights into their experiences with DDL.

Results and Discussions:

The results indicated several advantages of DDL in English language learning. Firstly, DDL promotes learner autonomy by providing learners with hands-on experience and empowering them to explore authentic language data. Learners can engage in personalized language exploration and identify patterns and structures through concordance analysis. Secondly, DDL enhances accuracy by exposing learners to real-life language examples and helping them understand language usage in context. This exposure to authentic language data allows learners to develop a more accurate understanding of grammar and vocabulary. Lastly, DDL fosters vocabulary development by enabling learners to identify collocations and lexical patterns through concordancers, thus expanding their vocabulary repertoire.

Although DDL offers numerous advantages, it also presents certain limitations. Firstly, DDL may lead to an overreliance on authentic language data, potentially neglecting other important language aspects such as register and style variation. It is crucial to strike a balance between authentic data and textbook language to ensure a comprehensive language learning experience. Secondly, DDL lacks individualized feedback, as learners primarily rely on self-guided exploration rather than receiving explicit corrective feedback from instructors. This absence of personalized feedback may hinder learners' ability to address specific language errors and hinder their progress in language proficiency.

Conclusion:

Data-driven learning has proven to be beneficial in enhancing English language learning in various ways. It promotes learner autonomy, enhances accuracy, and supports vocabulary development. However, educators should be

cautious of the potential overreliance on authentic language data and the lack of individualized feedback. Further research is needed to identify ways to integrate DDL effectively into language education to maximize its advantages and mitigate its limitations.

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